

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of Ag^+ in N-G.G. at ratios of N-G.G. : Ag^+ against NaOH (0.1M).

Fig. 2. Conductometric titrations of M/10 AgNO_3 against N-G.G.

KNO_3 and HClO_4 (2 mM) for initial lowering of buffer region in absence and presence of metal ion were carried out at 30° and 40° against 0.1M NaOH and the concentration of bound ligand, calculated from the horizontal distance between the corresponding curves, was divided by the metal ion concentration to obtain formation function \bar{n} . At any pH, the value of free ligand concentration (A) was calculated from the relation

$$[A] = \frac{[\text{N-GG}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{N-GG}]_{\text{Bound}}}{[\text{H}^+]\text{K}_a + 1}$$

Here N-GG = N-glycylglycine.

where K_a is the dissociation constant of N-glycylglycine⁷ is 8.5×10^{-9} . The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting \bar{n} vs. $-\log(A)$ reveal the formation of 1:1 complex. The log K values were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and found to be 8.01 and 8.055 at 30° and 40° respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the grant of research fellowship to one of them (S.P.B.) and to the Principal for providing research facilities.

References

1. R. S. SAXENA and G. L. KHANDELWAL, *Indian J. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **15A**, 757.
2. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA, *Monatshefte für Chemie*, 1977, **108**, 829.
3. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 532.
4. D. N. HUME, D. D. DEFORD and G. C. B. CAVE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5323.
5. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
6. J. BJERRUM, *Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions*, P. Hasse & Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. E. ARTHUR Martell & Robert, M. SMITH, "Critical Stability Constants", Vol. I, Aminoacids, Plenum Press (New York & England).

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes of Vanillideneanthranilic Acid and Vanillidenebromoanthranilic Acid

JESSY CHACKO and GEETHA PARAMESWARAN*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Calicut 673 635
Manuscript received 21 August 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

Calvin and Melchior's extension⁵ of Bjerrum's method⁶ has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes. The pH titrations of N-glycylglycine at ionic strength 0.1M

METAL chelates of the Schiff bases have been recently reviewed by Holm *et al.*¹. Copper acetylacetonanthranilic acid², copper N-(2-hydroxy-1 naphthalidene) anthranilic acid³,

N-bromosalicylideneanthranilic acid complexes of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)⁴ etc were recently prepared. In this preliminary communication we report the synthesis of several metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin and anthranilic acid or bromoanthranilic acid. It may be mentioned that this is the first report on the metal complexes of these ligands and we wish to make a comprehensive study of the co-ordination complexes of these ligands with various transition metal ions.

Preparation of Vanillideneanthranilic Acid :

A mixture of alcoholic solution of vanillin (1.52 g) and anthranilic acid (1.36 g) was refluxed for 1 hour. It was allowed to cool, water was added and the solution was left overnight in a refrigerator for crystallisation. Fine shining yellow crystals which were separated, were recrystallised from 1 : 1 ethanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. m.p. 174°.

Metal Complexes : These were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the metal chloride and the ligand in appropriate molar ratio in suitable solvents for about 5-6 hours. The solid complexes were filtered, washed with dry ethanol or ethyl acetate and dried in vacuum desiccator. Since most of these complexes have a low solubility in common organic solvents they were purified by subjecting to Soxhlet extraction in dry ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Based on elemental analysis the metal complexes display 1 : 2 or 1 : 1 stoichiometry and may possess the composition ML_2X_2 or $(MLX)_2$. The magnetic moments indicate the presence of 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electrons in Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and the remaining complexes were found to be diamagnetic. From these values it is apparent that Ti, Zr, Hf and Th complexes possess monomeric octahedral structure whereas the remaining planar complexes may exist as dimers. Negligibly small conductance values of the compounds suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The presence of the $\nu(OH)$ stretch in the infra-red spectra of the complexes indicate the monobasic character of the ligands. In the complexes $\nu C=O$ and $\nu C=N$ were shifted to lower frequency side due to complexation. As the complexes are insoluble in common solvents it was not possible to find out molecular weights and degree of polymerisation of the complexes.

Further studies in N.M.R., E.P.R., T.G.A., etc. are in progress and details will be reported in due course.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Professor S. S. Moosath for providing necessary facilities. The

authors are thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for awarding a fellowship to J. C. and financial assistance to G. P.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT (JR.) and A. CHAKRAVORTHY, *Progress in Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 88.
2. R. K. MEHTA, R. K. GUPTA and S. L. PANIA, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 687.
3. R. K. MEHTA, V. C. SINGI and S. L. PANIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 658.
4. G. C. SHIVAHARE and D. SHANKAR RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 785.

Complexes of Cu(II) and Cd(II) with Tetradentate Schiff's Bases

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA, S. S. DASH, S. K. PUJARI

Chemistry Department, Panchayat College, Bargarh, Sambalpur, Orissa

and

S. GURU

Chemistry Department, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack, Orissa,

Manuscript received 24 July 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

WE have been trying to synthesize new polydentate ligands in order to achieve rare co-ordination numbers through complexation of these ligands with some common divalent metal ions. In our earlier attempts, we have reported¹⁻⁴ complexes of a tridentate ligand, tri and tetradentate Schiff's bases using benzoin as the basic nucleus. In the present communication we have extended our investigation to the preparation of Cu(II) and Cd(II) complexes with tetradentate Schiff's bases derived from benzoin and ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine.

The method of preparation of the Schiff's bases have been mentioned in our earlier communication. Ethanolic solution of Cu(II) and Cd(II) chlorides were reacted with the Schiff's bases in 1 : 1 ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia with constant stirring when metal chelates separated out. These are filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on the solid specimen by Gouy method. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilgerwatt uvispeck spectrophotometer with M/100 (Chloroform ligand) solution of the complexes. The relevant analytical conductance